

Supplementary
Table S1. Farm-level distribution and coordinates (with centroids)

District	Farm	Examined (N)	Sampled (N)	Field-suspected (STRICT, N)	<i>A. hydrophila</i> (ML-confirmed) (N)	Farm centroid (lat, long: WGS84)
Mojokerto	Tawang Sari	20	9	14	1	-7.51194, 112.38167
Surabaya	Wonocolo	23	9	15	1	-7.34500, 112.72139
Surabaya	Keputih	12	5	8	1	-7.27694, 112.79583
Pasuruan	Pandaan	20	10	14	1	-7.65268, 112.68750
Blitar	Nglegok	18	4	12	1	-8.03500, 112.21728
Blitar	Selopuro	14	3	9	0	-8.13861, 112.25806
Blitar	Jeblog	18	4	12	0	-8.12028, 112.26167
Blitar	Tlogo	14	3	9	0	-8.12611, 112.19861
Blitar	Jingglong	23	5	16	1	-8.16455, 112.22978
Blitar	Kalipang	9	2	6	0	-8.16556, 112.21806
Blitar	Sawentar	27	6	19	1	-8.12472, 112.28611
Blitar	Jugo	18	4	12	0	-8.16118, 112.36703
Blitar	Pandanarum	23	5	15	1	-8.18195, 112.19330
Sidoarjo	Wadung Asri	18	4	12	0	-7.34528, 112.76972
Sidoarjo	Keboan Sikep	22	5	15	1	-7.38778, 112.72028
Totals		279	78	188	9	

*Examined (N)" = clinically screened fish; "Field-suspected (STRICT, N)" = fish meeting the field case definition (≥ 1 clinical sign in Table 2). STRICT counts are **estimates** derived from per-sign prevalences and will be replaced with exact farm-level values once the per-fish case listing is finalized. "*A. hydrophila* (multilocus)" denotes isolates confirmed by the multilocus workflow (16S plus rpoB and/or gyrB) described in Methods. Farm centroids are computed from Appendix 1.1 (WGS84, decimal degrees).

Table S2. Wilson 95% CI by Region. Regional prevalence of clinical signs in gourami (STRICT case definition).

Clinical sign	Region	x	N	Prevalence (%)	Lower 95% (%)	Upper 95% (%)
Anorexia (loss of appetite)	Blitar	3	164	1.8%	0.6%	5.2%
Anorexia (loss of appetite)	Mojokerto	1	20	5.0%	0.9%	23.6%
Anorexia (loss of appetite)	Pasuruan	0	20	0.0%	0.0%	16.1%
Anorexia (loss of appetite)	Sidoarjo	0	40	0.0%	0.0%	8.8%
Anorexia (loss of appetite)	Surabaya	2	35	5.7%	1.6%	18.6%
Ascites (abdominal fluid)	Blitar	9	164	5.5%	2.9%	10.1%
Ascites (abdominal fluid)	Mojokerto	1	20	5.0%	0.9%	23.6%
Ascites (abdominal fluid)	Pasuruan	1	20	5.0%	0.9%	23.6%
Ascites (abdominal fluid)	Sidoarjo	5	40	12.5%	5.5%	26.1%
Ascites (abdominal fluid)	Surabaya	1	35	2.9%	0.5%	14.5%
Bubbling via operculum	Blitar	2	164	1.2%	0.3%	4.3%
Bubbling via operculum	Mojokerto	0	20	0.0%	0.0%	16.1%
Bubbling via operculum	Pasuruan	0	20	0.0%	0.0%	16.1%
Bubbling via operculum	Sidoarjo	1	40	2.5%	0.4%	12.9%
Bubbling via operculum	Surabaya	2	35	5.7%	1.6%	18.6%
Digestive-tract damage	Blitar	0	164	0.0%	0.0%	2.3%
Digestive-tract damage	Mojokerto	0	20	0.0%	0.0%	16.1%
Digestive-tract damage	Pasuruan	0	20	0.0%	0.0%	16.1%
Digestive-tract damage	Sidoarjo	0	40	0.0%	0.0%	8.8%
Digestive-tract damage	Surabaya	1	35	2.9%	0.5%	14.5%

Exophthalmia	Blitar	28	164	17.1%	12.1%	23.6%
Exophthalmia	Mojokerto	4	20	20.0%	8.1%	41.6%
Exophthalmia	Pasuruan	0	20	0.0%	0.0%	16.1%
Exophthalmia	Sidoarjo	9	40	22.5%	12.3%	37.5%
Exophthalmia	Surabaya	5	35	14.3%	6.3%	29.4%
Fin erosion	Blitar	15	164	9.1%	5.6%	14.5%
Fin erosion	Mojokerto	0	20	0.0%	0.0%	16.1%
Fin erosion	Pasuruan	2	20	10.0%	2.8%	30.1%
Fin erosion	Sidoarjo	6	40	15.0%	7.1%	29.1%
Fin erosion	Surabaya	0	35	0.0%	0.0%	9.9%
Hemorrhagic lesions	Blitar	29	164	17.7%	12.6%	24.2%
Hemorrhagic lesions	Mojokerto	5	20	25.0%	11.2%	46.9%
Hemorrhagic lesions	Pasuruan	6	20	30.0%	14.5%	51.9%
Hemorrhagic lesions	Sidoarjo	10	40	25.0%	14.2%	40.2%
Hemorrhagic lesions	Surabaya	7	35	20.0%	10.0%	35.9%
Intestinal hemorrhage	Blitar	18	164	11.0%	7.1%	16.7%
Intestinal hemorrhage	Mojokerto	0	20	0.0%	0.0%	16.1%
Intestinal hemorrhage	Pasuruan	0	20	0.0%	0.0%	16.1%
Intestinal hemorrhage	Sidoarjo	0	40	0.0%	0.0%	8.8%
Intestinal hemorrhage	Surabaya	3	35	8.6%	3.0%	22.4%
Renal swelling	Blitar	22	164	13.4%	9.0%	19.5%
Renal swelling	Mojokerto	6	20	30.0%	14.5%	51.9%
Renal swelling	Pasuruan	3	20	15.0%	5.2%	36.0%
Renal swelling	Sidoarjo	7	40	17.5%	8.7%	31.9%
Renal swelling	Surabaya	0	35	0.0%	0.0%	9.9%
Scale loss / desquamation	Blitar	21	164	12.8%	8.5%	18.8%
Scale loss / desquamation	Mojokerto	0	20	0.0%	0.0%	16.1%
Scale loss / desquamation	Pasuruan	0	20	0.0%	0.0%	16.1%
Scale loss / desquamation	Sidoarjo	0	40	0.0%	0.0%	8.8%
Scale loss / desquamation	Surabaya	10	35	28.6%	16.3%	45.1%
Skin ulcers / open wounds	Blitar	20	164	12.2%	8.0%	18.1%
Skin ulcers / open wounds	Mojokerto	1	20	5.0%	0.9%	23.6%
Skin ulcers / open wounds	Pasuruan	8	20	40.0%	21.9%	61.3%
Skin ulcers / open wounds	Sidoarjo	2	40	5.0%	1.4%	16.5%
Skin ulcers / open wounds	Surabaya	4	35	11.4%	4.5%	26.0%
Sluggish swimming	Blitar	0	164	0.0%	0.0%	2.3%
Sluggish swimming	Mojokerto	2	20	10.0%	2.8%	30.1%
Sluggish swimming	Pasuruan	0	20	0.0%	0.0%	16.1%
Sluggish swimming	Sidoarjo	0	40	0.0%	0.0%	8.8%
Sluggish swimming	Surabaya	0	35	0.0%	0.0%	9.9%
Surface floating tendency	Blitar	3	164	1.8%	0.6%	5.2%
Surface floating tendency	Mojokerto	0	20	0.0%	0.0%	16.1%
Surface floating tendency	Pasuruan	0	20	0.0%	0.0%	16.1%
Surface floating tendency	Sidoarjo	0	40	0.0%	0.0%	8.8%
Surface floating tendency	Surabaya	0	35	0.0%	0.0%	9.9%

*Columns show counts (x/N), point estimates (%), and two-sided Wilson 95% confidence intervals per region (Mojokerto, Surabaya, Pasuruan, Blitar, Sidoarjo).

Table S3. Distribution of antibiotic resistance (%) of *A. hydrophila* isolates and MAR indices.

Bacterial Code	Isolate Source	No. of Resistant Antibiotics (All-18)	Resistance Profile	Number of Antibiotic Classes	R (All) /18	MAR Index (All-18)	R (Relevant)/11	MAR-Relevant (primary)	Stance Level
WS38	Gourami	10	STR, AMP, AZM, P, RIF, CFM, CLI, CFD, NB, VAN	9	10/18	0.556	4/11	0.364	MDR
TM25	Gourami	10	STR, AMP, AZM, P, RIF, CFM, CLI, CFD, NB, VAN	9	10/18	0.556	4/11	0.364	MDR
KS77	Gourami	11	STR, AMP, AZM, P, RIF, CFM, CLI, CFD, GEN, NB, VAN	9	11/18	0.611	5/11	0.455	MDR
PP26	Gourami	12	CHL, STR, AMP, AZM, P, RIF, CFM, CLI, CFD, GEN, NB, VAN	10	12/18	0.667	6/11	0.545	MDR
GB59	Gourami	14	CHL, STR, TET, AMP, AZM, P, RIF, ERY, CFM, CLI, CFD, GEN, NB, VAN	12	14/18	0.778	7/11	0.636	MDR
SB59	Gourami	16	CHL, STR, TET, AMX, AMP, AZM, P, RIF, ERY, CFM, CLI, CFD, GEN, NB, VAN, OXT	12	16/18	0.889	9/11	0.818	MDR
SB66	Gourami	16	CHL, STR, TET, AMX, AMP, AZM, P, RIF, ERY, CFM, CLI, CFD, GEN, NB, VAN, OXT	12	16/18	0.889	9/11	0.818	MDR
SS26	Gourami	17	CHL, STR, TET, AMX, AMP, AZM, P, DOX, RIF, ERY, CFM, CLI, CFD, GEN, NB, VAN, OXT	12	17/18	0.944	10/11	0.909	MDR
WS48	Gourami	17	CHL, STR, TET, AMX, AMP, AZM, P, DOX, RIF, ERY, CFM, CLI, CFD, GEN, NB, VAN, OXT	12	17/18	0.944	10/11	0.909	MDR

14

Table S4a. Dose–response summary: cumulative 7-day mortality (%), LD₅₀ estimates (Reed–Muench and probit, 95% CI), and classification of each dose as lethal (≥50%) or sublethal (≤20%).

15

16

Dose	Day-7 survival (%)	Day-7 mortality (%)	Mortality (n/N)	Window classification
Control (PBS)	100.0	0.0	0/30	– (control)
1×10 ⁴ CFU/mL	95.8	4.2	1/30	Sublethal (≤20%)
1×10 ⁵ CFU/mL	68.9	31.1	9/30	Intermediate (>20–<50%)
1×10 ⁶ CFU/mL	19.5	80.5	24/30	Lethal (≥50%)
1×10 ⁷ CFU/mL	9.7	90.3	27/30	Lethal (≥50%)
1×10 ⁸ CFU/mL	0.0	100.0	30/30	Lethal (≥50%)

*Group size per dose: 30 fish (3 tanks × 10 fish). Classification: Sublethal ≤20% mortality; Lethal ≥50%; Intermediate >20–<50%. Counts are rounded from Kaplan–Meier percentages; replace with raw deaths per dose if available.

17

18

Table S4b. LD50 estimates (with 95% CIs)

Estimator	LD50 (CFU/mL)	95% CI
Probit (weighted probit)	373,498	332,716 – 419,280
Reed–Muench (bootstrap CI)	241,319	119,378 – 398,107

*Probit CI from a linear probit fit (Haldane–Anscombe adjusted). Reed–Muench traditionally yields a point estimate; the 95% CI shown is a nonparametric bootstrap (binomial resampling, $n = 30$ per dose, $B = 10,000$). Estimates are concordant within $0.19 \log_{10}$ CFU (≤ 0.30 prespecified).

Table S5a. Early biofilm cell attachment (OD590) by isolate and omnibus test results (Time_h = 1).

Isolate	Mean_ OD590	SD_ OD590	N_biologi cal_reps	N_technical_wells_per_rep	Over all_test	F_stat	df_ between	df_ within	Global_ p_valSue
ATCC 35654	0,28	0,04	3	8	ANOVA	1,581395349	3	8	0,268286692
SB59	0,3	0,05	3	8	ANOVA	1,581395349	3	8	0,268286692
PP26	0,33	0,06	3	8	ANOVA	1,581395349	3	8	0,268286692
WS48	0,25	0,03	3	8	ANOVA	1,581395349	3	8	0,268286692

*Values are mean OD590 (Mean_OD590) \pm standard deviation (SD_OD590) from 3 biological replicates, each with 8 technical wells. Differences among isolates were tested using one-way ANOVA; F, df_between, df_within, and the global p -value are reported. The omnibus statistics (F and p) refer to the overall comparison and are repeated in each row for convenience. Tukey-adjusted pairwise results and effect sizes (Hedges' g , 95% CI) are provided in Supplementary Table S5b.

Table S5b. Tukey-adjusted pairwise comparisons for early biofilm cell attachment (OD590) by isolate (Time_h = 1).

Isolate_i	Isolate_j	Method	Adjusted_p	Alpha	Significant	Effect_size_metric	Effect_size	CI_lower_95	CI_upper_95
ATCC 35654	SB59	Tukey (after ANOVA)	0,1	0,05	No	Hedges g	-0,353380883	-1,656856662	0,950094895
ATCC 35654	PP26	Tukey (after ANOVA)	[0.42788736]	0,05	No	Hedges g	-0,784464541	-2,175360065	0,606430984
ATCC 35654	WS48	Tukey (after ANOVA)	[0.15763812]	0,05	No	Hedges g	0,67882251	-0,685127206	2,042772226
SB59	PP26	Tukey (after ANOVA)	[0.15763812]	0,05	No	Hedges g	-0,434571581	-1,749778644	0,880635482
SB59	WS48	Tukey (after ANOVA)	[0.42788736]	0,05	No	Hedges g	0,9701425	-0,475898857	2,416183858
PP26	WS48	Tukey (after ANOVA)	[0.77216178]	0,05	No	Hedges g	1,349238468	-0,236088024	2,934564961

*Pairwise contrasts were computed using Tukey's HSD following a one-way ANOVA on biological-replicate means ($n = 3$ per isolate; 8 technical wells each). Columns: Isolate_i / Isolate_j (pairs compared), Method (test used), Adjusted_p (Tukey-corrected p), Alpha (family-wise α), Significant (Yes/No at $\alpha = 0.05$), Effect_size_metric (Hedges' g), Effect_size (point estimate), and its 95% CI (CI_lower_95, CI_upper_95).